

THE EFFECT OF HEAT TREATMENT ON THERMAL STABILITY OF TI MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The microstructures of in situ synthesized (TiB+La₂O₃)/Ti composite after β and TRIPLEX heat treatment are investigated. The room temperature tensile properties of the titanium matrix composites (TMCs) are tested, and thermal stability is carried out at 873K, 923K and 973K for 100h, respectively. The results show that the microstructure of specimen after β heat treatment is widmanstätten, while it is similar to basketweave after TRIPLEX heat treatment. Room tensile properties of specimen after TRIPLEX heat treatment are better than those of β heat treatment. After thermal exposure, the strength of specimens treated by β and TRIPLEX heat treatment increases, while the ductility decreases sharply, this is attributed to the precipitation of Ti₃Al and silicides. The thermal stability of specimen after TRIPLEX heat treatment is better than that after β heat treatment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Titanium matrix composites (TMCs), reinforced with ceramic particles, have considerable potential for improving properties and service temperature and can be extensively applied in areas such as aerospace, advanced weapon systems and the automotive industry, because of their high specific strength, good specific modulus and resistance to elevated temperatures [1-7].

Thermal stability is the basic requirement for high temperature titanium alloys, especially in the aero-industry. After long-term thermal exposure, the ductility of near-alpha titanium alloy decreases and the tensile strength increases. These are mainly due to the surface oxidation and microstructure changes of the alloy. The microstructure changes include the decomposition of the residual beta phase, precipitation of the Ti₃Al phase and agglomeration and precipitation of silicide [8, 9]. Therefore, thermal stability of in situ synthesized TMCs become very important.

The purpose of the present work is to investigate the effect of heat treatment on thermal stability of in situ synthesized (TiB+La₂O₃)/Ti composite. The microstructure and reinforcements before and after thermal exposure is characterized. Moreover influence factors of thermal stability are discussed in this paper.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The in situ synthesized titanium matrix composites were melted twice in the vacuum consumable electrode furnace and then forged from Φ 580 mm to Φ 70 mm. The chemical compositions of the matrix alloy are similar with the near- α high temperature titanium alloy IMI834. The TiB whiskers and La₂O₃ were formed during the solidification processing as the following reaction:

The theoretical volume fraction of TiB and La₂O₃ was 1.82% and 0.58%, respectively. The beta transformation temperature of TMCs was approximately 1313K. Heat treatment methods of specimens are listed in Table1. As below, β_3 means TRIPLEX heat treatment, AC means air cooling, and WQ means water quenching. After heat treatment, the specimens of TMCs were exposed at 873K, 923K and 973K for 100h respectively.

Heat treatment methods	β phase district.	$\alpha+\beta$ phase district.	
β	1333K, 1h + AC	—	923K, 2h + AC
TRIPLEX (β_3)	1333K, 1h +WQ	1253K, 2h + AC	923K, 2h + AC

Table1. Heat treatment methods of TMCs

The gauge sections of the tensile specimens were 15mm \times 4mm \times 1.5mm. Room tensile tests were carried out using Zwick T1-Fr020TN materials testing machine at a strain rate of 10⁻³s⁻¹. High temperature tensile tests were carried out using CSS-3905 materials testing machine at a strain rate of 10⁻³s⁻¹. The oxide layer of the specimens after thermal exposure was lathed for room temperature tensile test.

Microstructure observations were examined by optical microscope (OM), Philips-CM 200 transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and JSM-6700F scanning electron microscope (SEM).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure of TMCs after heat treatment

Figure 1 shows the microstructure of TMCs before and after β and β_3 heat treatment. The microstructure of specimens after β heat treatment is widmanstätten as shown in Fig 1(b). The microstructure of first step of β_3 heat treatment is martensite. For second step of β_3 heat treatment, the specimens are annealed in $\alpha+\beta$ phase district, the martensite completely decomposed into α phase. The bound of β grain isn't obvious. The microstructure is basketweave in prior β gain in Figure 1(c). The reinforcements are stable after heat treatment without interfacial reaction.

Figure 1 The microstructure of TMCs before (a) and after heat treatment (b) β heat treatment (c) β_3 heat treatment

3.2 Tensile properties of TMCs after heat treatment

The room temperature tensile properties of TMCs after heat treatment are listed in table 2. It can be seen that the heat treatment plays an important role on the tensile properties of TMCs. In comparison with β heat treatment, both ultimate strength and ductility of specimens after β_3 heat treatment are enhanced, especially ductility of specimens, which increase 75%. The ductility of specimen with basketweave is better than that of widmanstätten. Therefore, the combination of ultimate strength and ductility of specimens after TRIPLEX heat treatment are better than those of β heat treatment at room temperature.

Room tensile properties	Heat treatment method	
	β	TRIPLEX (β_3)
σ_b (MPa)	1187	1220
δ (%)	8	14

Table2. Tensile properties of TMCs after heat treatment

Figure 2 shows SEM images of TMCs near fracture surface after room temperature tensile test, some TiB whiskers near fracture surface fractured, and the fractures of TiB whiskers are approximately perpendicular to the tensile direction. The fractures of TiB whiskers mean that TiB whiskers bear tensile stress in the processing of room temperature tensile. This fracture mechanism is quite typical for TMCs tested at room temperature. The crucial parameter, critical aspect ratio (ARc) (AR: length-to-diameter ratio) of the short fiber should be considered when tensile test is carried out. Stress distribution for a short fiber before the crack initiating is determined by whether its AR is higher or lower than ARc. If a short fiber with AR is lower than ARc, TiB whisker is “inefficiently strengthening” reinforcement. Interfacial debonding takes place before the crack of TiB whisker initiates. If a short fiber with AR is higher than ARc, the maximal tensile stress reaches the tensile strength for the fracture of TiB without interfacial debonding. TiB whiskers are “efficiently strengthening” reinforcement. Stress is transferred from matrix to TiB whiskers in the process of tensile test. With the increase of strain, TiB whiskers fracture and cavities around the TiB whiskers increase, which leads to concentrate of stress and specimen fracture. ARc of TiB whiskers is about 2.7 at room temperature [10]. Most TiB whiskers of the TMCs are higher than ARc. A lot of fractured TiB whiskers are observed in Figure2 (a) and Figure2 (b). The high aspect ratio of TiB whiskers is good for the load bearing effect. The dispersed small La_2O_3 particles are good for the dislocation density enhancement on the matrix. Although, the volume fraction of reinforcements is not very high, the enhancement of strength is significant [10-13].

Figure 2 SEM images of TMCs near fracture surface after room temperature tensile test, (a) β heat treatment, (b) β_3 heat treatment

3.3 Thermal stability of TMCs after heat treatment

Figure 3 shows tensile properties of TMCs after thermal exposure at 873K, 923K and 973K. In comparison with specimens without thermal exposure, only a slight change of ultimate strength has

been found for the specimens after thermal exposure. However, the ductility of specimens is sharply reduced after thermal exposure. With the increase of thermal exposure temperature, ultimate strength of TMCs increases as shown in Figure3 (a). After thermal exposure, ultimate strength of specimens treated by β_3 heat treatment is higher than that of β heat treatment. The ductility of all specimens is the worst at 923K thermal exposure. Compared with thermal exposure at 873K and 923K, the ductility of specimens shows an abnormal increase after thermal exposure at 973K in Figure3 (b). After thermal exposure, the ductility of specimens treated by β_3 heat treatment is better than that of β heat treatment in Figure 3(b).

Figure 3 Tensile properties of TMCs after thermal exposure, (a) ultimate strength (b) strain

Tensile test of TMCs after thermal exposure is carried out at room temperature. The fracture mechanism is similar with room temperature tensile test. Stress is distributed for TiB whiskers with high AR in the processing of tensile test.

Madsen [14] has reported that Ti_3Al precipitates are largely responsible for the increase in the yield strength and decrease in ductility of the near α -Ti1100 alloy at room temperature. Woodfield [15] has shown that reduction in ductility of the alloy, Ti-5331S (also known as IMI829) at room temperature was essentially due to silicides. The difference of microstructure between before and after thermal exposure is very small. But both α_2 - Ti_3Al and silicide particles are observed in TMCs after thermal exposure. Therefore, the effect of α_2 - Ti_3Al and silicide particles on thermal stability of TMCs must be considered. Both widmanstätten and basketweave are α and β platelet in prior β grain. So after thermal exposure, α_2 - Ti_3Al and silicide precipitates in TMCs of β heat treatment are similar with that of β_3 heat treatment. Only the precipitates in TMCs of β_3 heat treatment are discussed below.

Figure 4 shows dark field TEM micrograph of TMCs (β_3 HT) after thermal exposure and the selected area diffraction pattern. Very fine uniform precipitates are detected in Figure4 (a), (b) and (c). The super lattice diffraction pattern indicates that the precipitate in matrix should be the ordered intermetallic compound α_2 - Ti_3Al (Figure4 (c)). The orientation relationship may be deduced from this pattern: $(01\bar{1}\bar{1})_\alpha // (\bar{2}110)_{\alpha_2}$. With the increase of exposure temperature, the size of α_2 phase in the matrix increases. After thermal exposure at 973K for 100h, some of the α_2 precipitates' size is about 10 nm in diameter in Figure 4(c).

Figure 4 Dark field TEM micrograph of α_2 in TMCs (β_3) after thermal exposure, (a) 873K, 100h (b) 923K, 100h (c) 973K, 100h and selected area diffraction pattern

The silicide precipitation is heterogeneous in TMCs. Very fine silicides are observed at α/β interface of TMCs (β_3 HT) after thermal exposure in Figure 5. The size of silicides is about 20-100nm. Few silicides are observed in α platelet. With the increase of thermal exposure temperature, both particle size and volume fraction of silicides increase. The diffraction pattern indicates that the precipitate in selected area should be the $(\text{Ti, Zr})_5\text{Si}_3$ in Figure 5 (b). Both $(\text{Ti, Zr})_5\text{Si}_3$ (S_1) and $(\text{Ti, Zr})_6\text{Si}_3$ (S_2) are all hexagonal in structure. The S_1 and S_2 particles grow in the form of rod and ellipse respectively [16].

Figure 5 Bright field TEM micrograph of silicides in TMCs ($\beta_3\text{HT}$) after thermal exposure, (a) 873K, 100h (b) 923K, 100h and obtained diffraction pattern from selected area (c) 973K, 100h

Ti_3Al precipitates grow slowly and remain coherent even up to the size of 120 nm. The Ti_3Al particles (10nm) are coherent with matrix after thermal exposure. So, very fine Ti_3Al particles are cut by moving dislocations during deformation. The model developed by Gleiter and Hornbogen [17] for dislocations cutting the precipitates (ordered particles such as Ti_3Al), the increase in the critical resolved shear stress $\Delta\tau_0$, associated with the strengthening precipitates gives as follow:

$$\Delta\tau_0 = 0.28G^{-\frac{1}{2}}b^{-2}\gamma^{\frac{3}{2}}f^{\frac{1}{2}}r^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

Where $\Delta\tau_0$ is the critical resolved shear stress, G is the shear modulus, b the Burgers vector, γ is the antiphase boundary energy, f is the volume fraction of precipitates, and r is their radius. With particle size and volume fraction increasing, formula (2) indicates that the strength also increases [18].

The moving dislocations shear the precipitates, which makes the passage of additional dislocations easier. This process leads to a local reduction in the resolved shear stress along the active slip planes as deformation proceeding. The slip occurs preferentially on active slip planes, which is the cause of planar slip often observed in Ti alloys with short range ordering (i.e. precipitation of $\alpha_2\text{-Ti}_3\text{Al}$). The inhomogeneous slip distribution always leads to a considerable loss in the ductility and macroscopically brittle fracture. With the increase of particles size, the tendency of inhomogeneous slip increases drastically until particle-matrix interface is incoherent. The deformation mode changes

from dislocation shearing to dislocation looping, and then the homogeneity of deformation increases [19]. This can be easily understood considering the strengthening associated with shear particles. Ti₃Al precipitates are known to grow slowly and remain coherent even up to the size of 120 nm [20]. The changes of ductility and strength of specimens are mainly dominated by dislocation shearing after the thermal exposure at 873K, 923K or 973K. From 873K to 923K, with f and r increasing, $\Delta\tau_0$ increases, so the strength of specimen enhances increases, ductility decreases. The thermal exposure temperature of 973K is near the solution temperature of Ti₃Al. The nucleation amount of Ti₃Al decreases. At the 973K thermal exposure, r increases, but f reduces sharply, then $\Delta\tau_0$ decreases. So, after 973K thermal exposure, the critical resolved shear stress decreases, and the ductility of specimen increase.

The silicide particles are incoherent with matrix. The moving slip bands are pinned by silicide precipitation during deformation [21]. The stress is concentrated around silicide particles. Moreover, the coarse silicide particles are relatively brittle compared with the matrix and promote void initiation in tensile testing when planar arrays of dislocation meet the silicide particles [22].

The thermal stability decreases after thermal exposure, it is the result of both Ti₃Al and silicide precipitate, but it is difficult to judge which one plays the major role on thermal stability of TMCs.

After thermal exposure, few changes of microstructure are observed, the conditions of Ti₃Al and silicide precipitate in widmanstätten are similar to basketweave, and from Figure 3, it can be concluded that thermal stability of TMCs treated by β_3 heat treatment (basketweave) is better than that of β heat treatment (widmanstätten).

3.4. Effect of reinforcements on thermal stability

Figure 6 The TEM micrograph of the reinforcements treated by β_3 HT after 973K thermal exposure (a) TiB whisker (b) TiB diffraction pattern

Figure 6 shows the TEM microscopy of the reinforcements TiB whisker (β_3 HT) after thermal exposure. The TiB whiskers are stable without interfacial reaction after 973K thermal exposure for 100h. The size of La₂O₃ particles is about 200-300nm in Figure 6(a). Thus, it can be deduced that the TiB whiskers are stable without interfacial reaction after heat treatment at 873K, 923K and 973K for 100h, the stable reinforcements can ensure the stability of TMCs.

Figure 7 The TEM micrograph of the reinforcements treated by β_3 HT after 973K thermal exposure (a) La_2O_3 particle (b) La_2O_3 diffraction pattern

Figure 7 shows the TEM microscopy of the reinforcements La_2O_3 particle (β_3 HT) after thermal exposure. The size of La_2O_3 particles is about 200-300nm in Figure7(a). The La_2O_3 particles are stable without interfacial reaction after 973K thermal exposure for 100h. Formula (1) indicates La can reduce oxygen concentration in the matrix. The two main factors improving precipitate of Ti_3Al are electron concentration and Al content in matrix [23,24]. The oxygen has contributed enormously to enhance the electron concentration. The empirical formula “aluminum equivalent” (Al^*), $\text{Al}^* = \text{Al}\% + 1/3(\text{Sn}\%) + 1/6(\text{Zr}\%) + 10([\text{O}]\%) \leq 9$, can be introduced to control the alloying elements in near-alpha titanium alloys[25]. The coefficient of oxygen in “aluminum equivalent” formula is as high as 10. Oxygen may be the strongest promoting precipitate of Ti_3Al . So La can reduce oxygen concentration, depress precipitate of Ti_3Al . The reinforcement of La_2O_3 can improve the thermal stability of TMCs.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the effect of β and TRIPLEX heat treatment on tensile properties and thermal stability of in situ synthesized $(\text{TiB} + \text{La}_2\text{O}_3)/\text{Ti}$ composite are studied. It can be concluded as follows:

(1) The microstructure of TMCs after β heat treatment is widmanstatten. The microstructure after TRIPLEX heat treatment is similar with basketweave in prior β grain.

(2) Both tensile strength and ductility of TMCs after TRIPLEX heat treatment are better than those of β heat treatment at room temperature.

(3) Compared with TMCs without thermal exposure, ultimate strength of TMCs after thermal exposure increases slightly, the ductility sharply decreases. After thermal exposure, ultimate strength of TMCs treated by TRIPLEX heat treatment is higher than that of β heat treatment. The ductility of TMCs treated by TRIPLEX heat treatment is better than that of β heat treatment.

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